

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17985775

Nexus Of Forensic Accounting Practices And Private Sector Frauds In Nigeria

*Ukeni, Mgbechikwre Victoria, Prof. Ofurum .O. Clifford & Solomon Egbe, PhD

Department of Accounting
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria
*Email: Ukenivictoria@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The continuous upsurge in fraud and corruption in Nigeria necessitated the setting up of regulatory agencies to tackle the anomaly. Concurrently, there is a paradigm shift in the use of only traditional auditing tools for fraud investigations due to inadequacies necessitating the deployment of forensic accounting tools. This study therefore has the goal to examine the effect of forensic accounting tools in detection and prevention of private sector frauds in Nigeria in the long run for the period 1999 to 2024 using primary and secondary data. The study used Hausman test for selection of model and multiple regression for determination of relationship. Various diagnostic tests were carried out to ensure reliability of results. The autoregressive distributed lag was used to determine short run and long run impacts of forensic accounting tools on private sector fraud. Data mining and investigative accounting lead to reduction in Private sector Frauds in Nigeria. However, Litigation support has no significant effect on Private sector Frauds in Nigeria signalling the ineffectiveness of the judiciary in giving relevant support to the agencies saddled with the responsibility to detect and prevent frauds in the long run. The study has demonstrated that forensic accounting tools do not deliver long run effects on fraud reduction. There is also increased need for the private sector to strengthen internal controls and internal audit by exposing employees to necessary forensic accounting tools and employment of forensic accounting experts.

Keywords: Investigative Accounting, Data Mining, Litigation Support, Private Sector Frauds

INTRODUCTION

Fraud and economic crimes remain a perennial and challenging malaise impacting negatively on economic development (Osmond, Donald and Akemike ,2023) in Nigeria. The private sector plays a key role in economic development through provision of employment, and provision of goods and services. However, the occurrences of fraud internally impact organizations cash flows and effective operations of the business entity. The country has witnessed numerous high-profile frauds in private organizations leading to significant financial losses threatening the survival and smooth operations of the business igniting public outcry about corporate accountability. Many private businesses have suffered losses to frauds such as embezzlement, lading, larceny, insider trading, defalcations, financial statement manipulation, cash suppression and tax evasion. Fraud in Nigeria's private sector, particularly in banking, insurance and manufacturing industries, has led to financial losses and corporate failures. The Companies engaged in financial misstatement to inflate profits, leading to major forensic investigation. Many organizations lack robust fraud detection systems, making them vulnerable to financial crimes. Firm may manipulate revenue figures, inflate assets values, or understate liabilities to mislead stakeholders. The collapse of institutions, such as Diamond bank, Cadbury Nigeria Plc,2006; Oando, 2007; Oando plc,2017 intercontinental bank, oceanic Bank, and many others are evidences of frauds that affect financial stability of firms in Nigeria. Organizations respond to this anomaly by setting up internal control mechanisms in addition to regulatory requirements for external auditing. However, the failures of these strategies (Agbo et al, 2023; Osunwole et al.2024) coupled with increasing occurrence of frauds necessitated the deployment and implementation of forensic accounting tools as a panacea towards the detection and prevention of private sector frauds.

Forensic experts deploy data analytic techniques during assessment of financial statements, audit trails, and transactions records to determine inconsistencies and fraud indicators (Modugu & Anyaduba, 2013). Additionally, in recognition of the dangers of frauds to the economy the government established the economic and financial crimes and ICPC as regulatory agencies to help in the fight against frauds and other economic crimes.

Forensic accounting is a special technique which uses a combination of accounting, auditing and investigative skills to deter, detect and prevent frauds in a quest to provide legal support when the need arises in court. Investigative accounting, litigation support and data mining techniques are major tools deployed by experts in forensic accounting and these tools has significantly improved fraud detection and management in Nigeria. Scholars and professionals alike recognize the pivotal role of forensic accounting in enhancing financial transparency, ensuring accountability, and providing credible evidence for legal proceedings.

Despite the deployment of forensic accounting tools by many organizations, its efficacy and efficiency in achieving the goals and mitigating frauds has been a subject of debate. Reports from transparency international clearly indicates that frauds and financial crime is increasing and prevalent in Nigeria. Many empirical studies (Chigozie,2018; Ogah Idagu Joseph, 2025; Onyema, Ayodele and Adebayo,2024; Esonwune and Ogiri, 2024; Ndukah, Manasseh and Chin, 2025; Okoye and Ndah ,2019); Basse, 2019; Alkhalileh et.al. 2024; Okorafor ,2024; Muritala, Ijaiya, Afolabi, & Yinus, 2020; Offiong, Udoka and Ibor, 2016. Akinyomi, 2012) Okenwa and Chinchere, 2024; Subhi, Zubir, and Bayan (2020), Ahmeed et.al 2023; Akinyomi, 2012; Ibor, 2016) however have been carried out on the subject to determine the nature of relationship and effects of forensic accounting and frauds in Nigeria. The outcome of these studies is mixed and there is no consensus. Further, many of the studies (Jolaiya, 2024; Ugwu, 2021; Agbo et a,2023; Osunwole et al.2024; Okoye and Akamobi, 2009, *Onamusi* ,2024; Garba, 2024; Ede, Obinna and Patrick (2024);Egwakhe, Benjamin and Umukoro (2024); Udeh and Ugwu (2018); Kanu and Okorafor ,2013, Chiezey and Onu ,2013) Kiragu et al. 2013; Herbert et.al, 2017; Odhiambo, 2013) are industry specific focusing mainly on financial institutions (Basin , 2015; Adetiloye et al. 2016; Offiong et al.2016; Inaya and Isoto ,2016 ;Adeniyi, 2016), Osuala et al. 2016 ; Abubakar, Abubakar, and Hyellaki, 2022; Alao and Odum ,2019) ;Mutesi , 2020; Onibudo, 2017; Kanu, 2018; Sang, 2012; Kolapo and Olaniyan, 2020) without considering other sectors of the economy. Furthermore, the gap in the literature is further amplified by methodological differences which might impact findings. Holistically, the studies failed to capture numerically the relationship and impacts of forensic accounting tools on private sector frauds. Also, most prior studies failed to consider the long run implications of forensic accounting tools on frauds in Nigeria This study therefore deviates from prior study with the aim of ascertaining generally the effect of forensic accounting tools on private sector frauds in Nigeria on the long run using fraud statistics and forensic accounting tools. The study further attempts to decipher the preventive and detective roles of forensic accounting tools on frauds in the private sector in Nigeria. By exploring the role of forensic accounting in corporate fraud detection and prevention, this study will expose the necessity for forensic audit practices, data analytics, and fraud risk assessments.

2.0 Literature

2.1 Conceptual Literature

2.1.1 Forensic Accounting

Forensic accounting is a specialized field of accounting that involves applying investigative and analytical skills to resolve financial disputes, fraud cases, and legal matters. It combines elements of accounting, auditing and legal expertise to detect fraudulent activities, assess financial damages, and provide evidence for litigation. The American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA) defines Forensic accounting as the application of accounting principles, investigative techniques, and legal knowledge to assist in dispute resolution and fraud detection. Forensic accounting has also been defined as the application of accounting, auditing and investigative skills to resolve legal issues and detect fraud (Crumbley, Heitger, & Smith, 2013). This field of accounting plays a crucial role in preventing and detecting financial crimes by ensuring transparency and accountability in financial reporting (Apostolou, Hassell, & Webber, 2000).

2.1.1 Investigative Accounting

Albrecht et al. (2012) define investigative accounting as the fusion of accounting knowledge and investigative techniques aimed at exposing financial misconduct. In Nigeria, investigative accounting is particularly valuable for detecting corporate fraud, uncovering government misappropriation, tracing hidden

assets, and assessing financial statement integrity Investigative accounting is a critical aspect of forensic accounting that focuses on detecting financial anomalies and uncovering fraudulent transactions. It involves the examination of financial records, interview with key personnel, and the application of forensic techniques to gather evidence of fraud (Albrecht, 2018). Investigative accounting is a key pillar of forensic accounting, focusing on the systematic examination of financial records to detect anomalies. It involves tracing illicit funds, reconstructing fraudulent transactions, and identifying discrepancies that may indicate fraudulent activities. Agbo et al. (2023), examined the role of investigative accounting in fraud prevention within Nigeria deposit money banks (DMBs). The study revealed that investigative accounting enhances the effectiveness of fraud detection mechanisms.

2.1.2 Litigation Support

Litigation support is another function of forensic accounting that involves the preparation of expert reports, financial evidence, and professional testimony in legal proceedings (Hopwood, Leiner & Young, 2012). Fraud cases often require forensic accountants to provide litigation support by analyzing financial data, evaluating economic damages, and assisting legal teams in understanding complex financial transactions (Crumbley, 2013), Owojori and Asaolu (2009) describe litigation support as the factual presentation of economic issues related to litigation, where forensic accountants quantify financial losses and provide insights that guide judicial decisions.

2.1.3 Data Mining

Data mining is a forensic accounting tool used to detect fraudulent patterns and anomalies in financial data. It involves the use of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and statistical modeling to identify suspicious transactions and predict potential fraud risks (Ngai, 2011). Fayyad, Piatetsky-Shapiro, and Smyth (2006) define data mining as the extraction of meaningful patterns from large datasets using computational tools. In Nigeria, where data integrity issues and fraudulent financial practices are prevalent, data mining enhances fraud detection capabilities in both public institutions and private organizations

2.2 Theoretical Underpinning

Many theoretical postulations have been made relating to fraud. However, this study is anchored on agency, fraud diamond and white-collar job theories. The **Agency theory** postulated by Jensen and Mecklings (1976) recognizes conflicts of interest arising between owners and employees of a business. It highlights that employees may deviate from organizational goals to pursue selfish interest thereby creating misalignment of goals. Such misalignment could be motivated by several factors including self-aggrandizement. Fraud on its own is self-motivated to satisfy the selfish desire of an employee that could involve financial statement manipulation, suppression and embezzlement of cash, theft of assets, insider trading and numerous other fraud strategies. Thus, fraud from agency perspective, is an agent principal conflict and desires specific remediation and prevention strategies such as internal control, auditing and fraud examination.

Fraud diamond theory (Wolfe and Hermanson, 2004) while agreeing with the agency theory and Fraud Triangle theories highlights the essential factors that make frauds occur. First, the fraudster must have certain motivations including undue self-inflicted pressure to fulfill a certain need. These needs could take different dimensions. Many prior studies (Johnson et al. 2003; Denis et al. 2005; Hernandez and Groot, 2007; Efendi et al.2007; Lie, 2005; Burns and Kedia ,2006) found incentives and undue pressure as the motivation for fraud. Closely associated with the incentive to commit fraud is the opportunity to commit fraud. Organizations set up control mechanisms in form of checks and balances to curtail errors, prevent frauds and ensure smooth running of the organization. However, for frauds to succeed the fraudster must be able to circumvent the checks and balances or create a loophole to carry out the fraudulent activities. In the fraud diamond theory, this is classified as opportunity. Many studies (Beasley, 1996; Albrecht and Albrecht, 2003; Dechow et al. 1996; McMullen and Raghunandan, 1996; Farber, 2005) confirm that weak and non-existent internal control mechanisms create opportunities for fraud. Therefore, opportunity must be present before a fraudster is able to exploit this loophole to commit fraud. In addition to the opportunity, the fraudster will carry out self-assessment to justify the fraudulent activity and provide conviction for the fraud. This is referred to as rationalization. Many fraudsters in corporate organizations may explain their behaviors through arguments such as poor pay, denial of promotion, ignorance that it's a crime and borrowing with intent to refund. But beyond all these factors, is the ability to commit fraud, this is the dimension that distinguishes fraud diamond theory from the fraud triangle. Whilst the fraud triangle (Cressey,1953) recognizes the presence of pressure, opportunity and rationalization as the ingredients necessary for fraud, the fraud diamond theory (Wolfe and Hermanson, 2004) argues that no fraudster is able to commit fraud

without the capacity and ability to carry out the fraud. Fraud diamond theory recognizes the pressure, opportunity, rationalization and in addition ability as the fourth factor before fraud can be achieved.

White collar Job Theory (Sutherland, 1939) espoused abuse of trust by people in positions of power and influence such as business executives, politicians, and professionals. Most frauds are committed as a result of offices and positions of authority and occupation. Unlike street crimes, white-collar crimes are non-violent offenses that involves deception, manipulations, and abuse of trust for financial gain. These crimes are typically committed in corporate and government settings and include fraud, embezzlement, insider trading and money laundering. First the theory recognizes abuse of power. Secondly it highlights that White-collar crimes often involve complex financial transactions that makes detection difficult. Fraudsters may use sophisticated accounting tricks, shell companies such as special Purpose Vehicles, related party transactions and offshore accounts to conceal their activities. White collar crimes often rationalize their actions to justify unethical behavior whilst taking advantage of weak regulatory framework or legal loopholes to avoid prosecution.

2.3 Empirical Review.

Ndukah, Manasseh and Chin (2025) examined forensic auditing influences on bank performance in Nigeria, using annual data from 2013 to 2023. Using autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model findings revealed forensic auditing is crucial in enhancing financial reporting accuracy, fraud detection, and risk management whilst also minimizing fraudulent activities and ensuring compliance with regulatory standards and fosters secure and efficient banking environment. Ngum (2025) assessed influence of forensic accounting on performance of MFIs in Mezam, Cameroun. Result revealed forensic accounting increases performance and both forensic audit and forensic litigation positively affect performance of MFIs but the effect of forensic litigation was positive and insignificant. Oranefo and Ufaroh (2025) examined link between forensic accounting and fraudulent activities in Delta State corporate firms. Outcome revealed significant relationship between forensic accounting, fraud prevention and fraud detection in selected firms in Delta State

Jolaiya (2024) investigated effect of electronic fraud on financial performance of banks in Nigeria. The study concluded that electronic fraud has significant negative relationship with the performance of banks. Alkhalaleh et.al. (2024) examined effect of auditors and forensic accounting skills impacts financial performance of audited companies. Outcome of study revealed external auditors with forensic accounting competencies have a positive impact on the financial performance of audited companies. Oladutire, Afolabi and Adesanya (2024) examined effect of forensic accounting on financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBS) in Nigeria, between 2012 and 2021. Findings revealed forensic accounting has significant effect on financial performance when measured using profit after tax. Kankpang and Anipuye (2024) examined forensic accounting effects on fraud prevention and detection in Nigeria banks. Using survey approach, study revealed significant relationship between litigation support services, crime investigation services and documentation and reporting as forensic accounting functions and prevention of fraud in banks. Joseph et.al (2024) tried to determine influence of forensic accounting on detection and prevention of fraud in banks. Using survey method, findings revealed forensic accounting tools significantly influenced fraud detection and prevention in First Bank Nigeria Plc. Akadi and Gideon (2024) examined forensic accounting and corporate fraud in Nigerian deposit money banks. Study outcome revealed positive and significant effect on fraud detection and prevention in deposit money institutions through forensic review, forensic inspection, and forensic documentation. Okorafor (2024) investigated influence of forensic accounting skills on fraud investigation on Enugu Electricity Distribution Company. Study found forensic accounting skills, investigative flexibility, accounting and auditing expertise, analytical proficiency, and communication skills have positive and significant impacts on fraud. Ozigbo and Arife (2023) investigated forensic accounting and corporate fraud prevention. The study concluded forensic accounting tools used by firms in Delta State reduces cases of fraud

Obiora and Asah (2022) examined the effect of forensic assurance services on fraud detection and prevention in manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Findings confirmed fraud detection, prevention, and forensic assurance services at 1% significant level have a positive and significant relationship. Babalolola (2022) examined forensic accounting impact financial performance and growth of MTN mobile communication in Nigeria and found a significant relationship between forensic accounting and growth in financial performance

Owolabi and Ogunsola (2021) studied forensic auditing helps in detection and prevention of fraud in Nigerian deposit money banks using Ibadan metropolis branches. The findings indicated that skills forensic accounting, legal background, knowledge of procedures, and expertise in forensic accounting significantly

contribute to fraud prevention. Agboare (2021) examined the role of forensic accountancy on financial irregularity uncovering in deposit money banks in Nigeria with the focus on the effectiveness of conducting enquiry on financial misstatement discovery and to know whether re-establishing incomplete accounting data can be effective in disclosing financial scam in DMBS. Using primary data, study found forensic accounting procedure of enquiry, scrutinizing financial records and reconstruction of partial accounting proceedings have a way or influence on misstatement discovery in DMBS in Nigeria. Tapang & Ihendinihu, (2020) assessed the effect of forensic accounting fraud investigations on unethical practices in the Nigerian banking sector revealing that mortgage fraud, credit card fraud, and check fraud are all significantly impacted by forensic accounting fraud investigations. Lawal, Yinusa, Lawal, Oyetunji & Adekoya (2020) studied effect of forensic accounting on fraud detection in the manufacturing industry in Nigeria. The findings reveal an effect of forensic accounting on fraud detection is significantly highlighting its crucial role in identifying and addressing fraudulent activities. Alhassan (2020) conducted a study to evaluate the relationship between forensic accounting and fraud detection and prevention within the Nigerian public sector. Research utilized a survey design. Study found forensic accounting is also effective in fraud prevention.

Okoroyibo and Omorepie (2019) assessed the influence of forensic accounting on the output of Nigerian banking industry where attention was focused on the assessing of the influence of forensic investigation on the NPM of selected banks in the country and to evaluate the role of forensic investigation on retained earnings and dividend per share of Nigerian banking system. Secondary source of data collection was employed in which the annual report and account for (12) twelve years (2007-2018) were evaluated. The study revealed that NPM, PAT and DPS were majorly influenced by forensic audit. Okoye and Ndah (2019) investigated the association between forensic accounting and fraud prevention, focusing specifically on manufacturing companies operating in Nigeria. The findings indicated that, the implementation of forensic accounting practices significantly contributes to fraud prevention within manufacturing organizations in Nigeria. Bassey (2019) examined “the role and effects of forensic accounting in reducing financial crimes (fraud) in microfinance institutions, with a focus on microfinance banks in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria, using a survey research design. The study demonstrated the importance of forensic accounting investigative skills in reducing fraud in Nigerian microfinance institutions. Okoye (2019) studied influence of an expert witness testimony on prevention and detection of fraud within deposit money banks in Nigeria. study confirmed relationship between an expert witness testimony and both fraud detection and prevention are statistically significant. Ugwu (2021) examined application of forensic accounting in fraud detection, investigation and litigation support services. Outcome revealed forensic accounting contributes significantly in fraud control without completely obliterating frauds. Olaoye and Ogunleye (2019) assessed effect of forensic accounting techniques in Fraud prevention among Nigerian firms. Result indicated firms that engage forensic accountants experience fewer financial losses and forensic accounting techniques significantly reduces fraud cases in Nigeria firms by improving fraud detection and risk management.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted longitudinal research design using interview and questionnaires to obtain responses from employees of regulatory agencies for the independent variables then the responses are converted to numerical figures using a binary system. Contrastingly, the fraud figures which are secondary data expressed in monetary terms were obtained from regulatory agencies before being converted using natural logarithms.

3.2 Sampling and Sampling Method

The sample used in this study consisted of 25 years (1999-2024) observations which was considered a good representative of the population and adequate for reliable empirical results based on data availability. Using a purposive sampling method based on data availability and ease of obtaining information from EFCC and ICPC and the availability of information at Federal office of statistics website. The study administered 500 questionnaires to staff of the regulatory agencies involved in forensic investigation and obtained responses. Statistics and fraud figures were obtained from annual reports from Federal office of statistics, Nigeria financial institution training Centre, Independent Corrupt Practices and other related offences (ICPC) and Economic and Financial crimes commission (EFCC), and World Bank. However, for the purpose of examining the strategies used by EFCC and ICPC to investigate fraud we use questionnaire to obtain responses and thereafter code it to a binary system to convert data collected to quantitative data. The data was downloaded from the official website of the above-named sources; hence, desk method was used for

data collection. The time dimension on the variables allows for better panel analysis which eliminates some of the errors involved in time series data or cross-sectional data. For the independent variables content analysis was carried out. The questionnaire elicits a Yes or No response from respondents. A binary system is then employed to code the data. Assign the value 1 to answers on the affirmative and 0 to the answers 'NO' this assumes that forensic investigative tools play a role in fostering or reducing frauds in Nigeria. If employed assign the value 1 if not assign zero. The responses were further categorized for a question to be assigned the value of yes sixty percent of the respondents must answer yes to a particular question otherwise 0. The amounts in naira for frauds were further converted to natural log to facilitate reliability of the measurement

3.3 Variables of the study

The independent variable used in the study is Forensic accounting. When there is use of investigative accounting, Litigation support and data mining the value 1 is assigned and when it is not in use the value 0 is assigned. For forensic accounting the study examined it from two perspective detection and prevention with each tool being examined in this context. Thus, we have six proxies with each tool having the feature of detection and prevention. Litigation support, Data Mining and Investigative accounting. The length of time any forensic tool is used and the years is provided by EFCC and ICPC to facilitate a panel data framework that enabled the researcher answer the relevant research questions. The dependent variable for this study is private sector fraud which occurred annually over a period of twenty-five years and is measured in monetary terms and converted to natural log. Measurement of the variables are summarized on the table below:

Measurement of Variables summarized on Table 3.1 below:

Independent Variable	Measurement	Expected Sign
Investigative Accounting Detection (IVAD)	Assigned value of 1 when used as a detective tool otherwise 0	Negative
Litigation Support Detection (LITD)	Assigned value of 1 when used as a detective tool otherwise 0	Negative
Data Mining Detection (DATD)	Assigned value of 1 when used as a detective tool otherwise 0	Negative
Investigative Accounting – Prevention (IVAP)	Assigned value of 1 when considered as effective in fraud prevention with 60% Yes otherwise 0	Negative
Litigation support- - Prevention (LITP)	Assigned value of 1 when considered as effective in fraud prevention with 60% Yes otherwise 0	Negative
Data Mining – Prevention (DATP)	Assigned value of 1 when considered as effective in fraud prevention with 60% Yes otherwise 0	Negative
Dependent Variable		
Private sector Fraud)	Natural log of Annual figures of fraud that occurred in the private sector as published by FOS, CBN, EFCC and ICPC	Negative

3.8 Model specification

In an attempt to examine the effect of Forensic accounting on Private sector Frauds in Nigeria, the study modifies the model in the works of Idris and Suleiman (2019) and Inyama (2013). In line with their models, the model for this study is formulated as follows:

The functional relationship based on the dependent and independent variable is stated thus:

From the functional relationship we derive the estimation thus:

$$PRVF = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IVAD + \beta_2 DATD + \beta_3 LITD + \beta_4 IVAP + \beta_5 DATP + \beta_6 LITP + U_1, t \dots\dots\dots(i)$$

Estimation techniques

Unit root test

To prevent spurious result, stationarity was examined using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) technique developed by Dickey and Fuller (1979) was employed. This test is necessary as it guides the study on the selection of appropriate estimation techniques required for the analysis.

Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL)

Following the unit root test, the study proceeds to examine short and long run relationship among the variables. This is done using autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) known as the bound test approach to co-integration

In line with Pesaran et al. (2001), the unrestricted error correction mechanism for testing co-integration among the variables used in this study is stated as follows:

$$\Delta PRSF_t = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_1 \Delta \text{Log DATD}_{t-1} + \beta_0 + \sum \beta_1 \Delta \text{Log LITD}_{t-1} + \sum \beta_2 \Delta \text{Log IVAD}_{t-1} + \sum \beta_3 \Delta \text{Log IVAP}_{t-1} + \sum \beta_4 \Delta \text{Log LITD}_{t-1} + \sum \beta_2 \Delta \text{Log DATP}_{t-1} + \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \Delta \text{Log DATD}_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \Delta \text{Log LITD}_{t-1} + \alpha_3 \Delta \text{Log IVAD}_{t-1} + \alpha_4 \Delta \text{Log IVAP}_{t-1} + \alpha_5 \Delta \text{Log LITP}_{t-1} + \alpha_6 \Delta \text{Log IVAD}_{t-1} + U_1, t \dots\dots\dots (xviii)$$

The ARDL long-run model is estimated if cointegration is found while the short-run model is estimated if otherwise

$$\Delta PRSF = \dots \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Log DATD}_{t-1} + \beta_2 \text{Log LITD}_{t-1} + \beta_3 \text{Log IVAD}_{t-1} + \beta_4 \text{Log IVAP}_{t-1} + \beta_5 \text{Log LITP}_{t-1} + \beta_6 \text{Log DATP}_{t-1} + U_1,$$

$$\Delta PRSF = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \sum \Delta \text{Log DATD}_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \sum \Delta \text{Log LITD}_{t-1} + \alpha_3 \sum \Delta \text{Log IVAD}_{t-1} + \alpha_4 \sum \Delta \text{Log IVAP}_{t-1} + \alpha_1 \sum \Delta \text{Log LITD}_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \sum \Delta \text{Log DATP}_{t-1} + \text{ECM} + U_3 \dots \dots \dots (xii)$$

RESULTS

4.1.1 Trend Analysis

The trends in private sector fraud in the country, shown in Figure 4.1, indicates that there were periods of relatively low private sector frauds in the early 2000s. As from early 2010’s public sector fraud increased massively and has remained high since then, reaching over 35 percent in 2022. Thus, it is seen that private sector fraud has remained a major challenge in the country

Fig. 4.1: Trends in PRSF

4.1.2 Summary Statistics

Average private sector fraud is 10.56 percent, which is double digit and shows that private sector frauds has remained high in Nigeria. The standard deviation of 15.42 is higher than the mean value which indicates that private sector frauds has increased significantly value over the years.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics for Panel Data

Variable	Mean	Max.	Min.	Std. Dev.	Skew.	Kurt.	J-B	Prob
PRSF	10.56	35.00	1.90	8.42	1.39	4.26	20.05	0.00
IVAD	23.77	176.36	-82.24	42.59	1.13	5.79	27.89	0.00
DATD	27.39	166.67	-78.57	52.07	0.91	4.01	9.34	0.01
LITD	37.18	860.00	-87.80	123.74	5.81	39.17	3126.02	0.00
IVAP	120.59	5136.53	-99.88	709.62	6.99	49.91	5190.70	0.00
DATP	2.67	3.11	2.28	0.18	0.60	3.32	3.37	0.19
LITP	29.63	55.02	7.52	10.38	-0.19	2.72	0.50	0.78

The average growth rates of use of Forensic accounting tools variables are reported in the Table. Average growth rate of litigation support stood at 37.18 percent per annum is highest among the tools employed. Thus, it is seen that the use of litigation support increased at a significant rate than the use of investigative accounting over the years. There were periods of significant use of forensic accounting tools especially litigation support as shown by a maximum growth rate of 860 percentage points). Average effectiveness of data mining is 2.67 per annum over the study period. While that of litigation support is 29.63 indicating

litigation support is more effective than data mining. However average effectiveness for investigative accounting stood at 129.59.

4.1.3 Correlation

An important aspect to consider for the variables is the fact that the three measures of forensic accounting are likely to be highly correlated. This is because, forensic investigation is generally incremental in nature and responds to changes in fraud trends which significantly increases over time and tends to move both in data mining and Litigation support. This implies that variables used in a single estimation may exhibit the problem of multicollinearity.

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix

Probability	DATE						
	PRSF	IVAD	DATD	LITD	IVAP	P	LITP
PRSF	1.000 -----						
IVAD	0.8733 0.00	1.000 -----					
DATD	0.8141 0000	0.985 0.00	1.000 -----				
LITD	0.815 0.00	0.998 0.00	0.974 0.00	1.000 -----			
IVAP	0.7822 0.00	0.939 0.00	0.899 0.00	0.947 0.00	1.000 -----		
DATP	0.751 0.00	0.804 0.00	0.765 0.00	0.812 0.00	0.808 0.00	1.000 -----	
LITP	-0.019 0.89	-0.125 0.31	-0.081 0.50	-0.143 0.30	-0.177 0.20	0.037 0.79	1.000 -----

Among the Forensic accounting variables, there is a strong positive correlation among the three variables. Indeed, the correlation coefficient between IVAD and LITD is 0.998, while it is 0.985 with DATD. Also, DATD is correlated with LITD with a coefficient of 0.974. This shows that the correlations among the forensic variables are too large for these variables to be included in a single equation. In order to minimise the problem of multicollinearity in the estimates, the three variables are estimated in a recursive way. With this method, the effects of each variable on frauds are observed without encountering multicollinearity.

4.2 Tests for Time Series Properties of Dataset

4.2.1. Test for Normality of Data

The normality test for this study is based on Kernel tests for the variables as reported below. Normally distributed density functions indicate absence of heterogeneity-based estimation issues. From result no variables is normally distributed since the kernel plots are all concentrated away from the centre and meets expectation from heterogeneous data set obtained as a pool from different responses from different investigative organisations over different time periods negating use of OLS estimation

Fig. 4.8a: Kernel Density Test for PRSF

Fig. 4.8b Kernel Density Test for LITD

Fig. 4.8c: Kernel Density Test for IVAD

Fig. 4.8d: Kernel Density Test for

DATD

4.3. Unit Root and Cointegration Analysis

In this study, the test for stationarity of the data series is performed using two different methods namely, the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and the Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) procedure. The results of the unit root tests are presented in Table 4.3

Table 4.3: Unit Root test for Variables

Table 4.3: Unit Root test for Variables

Variable	ADF Test		KPSS		Order of Integration
	Levels	First Difference	Levels	First Difference	
<i>PRSF</i>	-0.133	-5.960**	0.758**	0.176	I(1)
<i>IVAP</i>	-1.012	-7.003**	0.512**	0.140	I(1)
<i>IVAD</i>	-3.263*	-3.454*	0.586*	0.205	I(0)
<i>DATD</i>	-0.358	-8.727**	0.968*	0.193	I(1)

<i>LITD</i>	0.804	-5.373**	0.841**	0.273	I(1)
<i>DATP</i>	-3.273*	-3.171*	0.144	0.991**	I(0)
<i>LITP</i>	-2.938*	-3.085*	0.252	0.498*	I(0)

Note: * indicates signifies at 5 percent; 95% critical values are reported in parentheses below each test value

From ADF tests result reported in first panel of Table 4.3, test statistics for variables in levels (IVAD) are less than the 95 percent critical values indicating insignificance. Conversely, statistic values for series in first differences are greater than critical values at 5 percent significance level. Thus, these variables are non-stationary in levels although their first differences were stationary. This implies that most of the variables in the study are integrated of order one (or I[1]). On the other hand, IVAD, DATP and LITP is integrated of order zero (or I[0]).

The KPSS test for stationarity improves robustness of unit root tests and is relevant in identifying actual stationarity patterns of the series while also whether the series are stationary or not and not in reference occurrence of unit roots. The result shown in the second panel of Table 4.3 indicates that for each of the series, the null hypotheses of stationarity cannot be rejected for the variables in first differences (the tests statistics fail the test This indicates that the series are difference-stationary and that most of the variables are actually I[1]. This implies that a dynamic long run relationship may be estimated based on the ARDL approach to cointegration for the dynamic analysis. Essentially, it is appropriate to use cointegration analysis to estimate the relationships between the variables.

The tests of stationarity provide grounds for examining the long run properties of the dataset in terms of cointegration analysis. From the unit root tests, it is seen that most of the variables are I(1) while three are I(0). Thus, there is the need to establish the cointegration status of the data in order to determine the long run equilibrium relationship among the variables. Note that not all variables in the model are integrated of the same order. Hence, the test for common stochastic trends or cointegration is performed using Bounds cointegration test procedure in order to further determine the long run time series properties. The evaluation of the Bounds cointegration results shown in Table 4.4 is based on the critical F-statistic values for the lower and upper bounds as also reported in the results. This test is interpreted based on the following procedure: if at any significance level, the estimated F-value is greater than both the lower test (I0 Bounds) and the upper test (I1 Bounds) values, then there is no cointegration among the variables. If the estimated F-value lies between the two Bounds values, then there is need to proceed with a lesser structure of the ARDL analysis. However, if the estimated value lies above both Bounds test values, then there is clear cointegration among the variables. Note that the test is conducted for the two equations that explain fraud

Table 4.4: Bounds Cointegration Test

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
<i>Eqn: PRVSF</i>				
F-statistic		10%	2.37	3.2
K		5%	2.79	3.67

The results in Table 4.4 indicate that the computed F-values for the Bounds test for each of the equations of 8.41 are all larger than both the I(0) and I(1) Bounds tests at the 5 percent. The F-values therefore pass the significance test at the 5 percent level for all the fraud estimated equations. Thus, a long run relationship is established between frauds in both the frauds variables and other variables in the model. This provides a strong background for the analysis of the ARDL model in the study.

4.4Regression Analysis

ARDL technique is used to estimate the relationships between the Forensic accounting tools and fraud in this study. This process of ARDL analysis require lag selection procedure to determine optimal lag length that expresses the relationship.

4.4.1 Lag Length Selection

optimality of the model was established using Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Schwarz–Bayesian

Criterion (SC). The results are presented in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: Lag Length Selection Criteria

No of Lags	PUBSF		PRSVF	
	AIC	SC	AIC	SC
0	3.62	3.9	2.91	1.25
1	-2.5	-0.78	-0.93	-0.38
2	-1.36	-1.74	-1.89	-1.52
3	-2.46	-1.44	-1.08	-0.63
4	-4.62*	-3.09*	-2.73*	-2.85
5	-1.82	-1.33	-2.68	-1.49

Note: * indicates selected lag.

The optimum lag length is determined by considering least values for test of coefficients. From result each of the equations (using the two frauds variables), the fourth lag possesses the minimum value. Given the AIC test for the equation as well as all the other equations, select the fourth lag, four lags are selected as optimal for all equations implying first four lags are expected to be retained for VECM estimation.

4.4.2 Analysis of ARDL Results

As indicated earlier, the ARDL procedure generates two estimates for the equations: the short run estimates and the long run estimates. Both of the estimates are interpreted and analysed in this section. It should be noted that the cointegrated results were obtained based on the lag selection test performed earlier. The diagnostic test in each of the equations is based on the adjusted R-squared values. This provides a consistent structure for the investigation of the dynamic relationship between the forensic accounting tools and each of the measure’s frauds in Nigeria.

Forensic Accounting and Private sector Frauds

The results for the effects of forensic accounting on private sector frauds are shown in Table 4.6. The diagnostic indicators of the results are relatively impressive, with the adjusted R-squared values for the three equations ranging from 0.432 to 0.582. This implies that, for the equation with data mining, over 58 percent of the systematic variations in Private sector frauds was explained in the specification. The D.W. coefficients are also in the expected range. The effects of Forensic accounting tools and other variables on public sector fraud are observed by considering the coefficients of the individual explanatory variables. In the short run results (reported in the upper panel), the coefficient of Investigative accounting did not feature in the short run estimates. This clearly shows that investigative accounting does not contribute to private sector frauds in Nigeria. Perhaps a more disaggregated forensic accounting pattern will provide clearer explanation of movements in private sector frauds in Nigeria. This is shown by the short run results for the equation with Data mining. In the equation, the coefficients of both Litigation support and data mining pass the significance test at the 1 percent level and is positive. This shows that data mining and Litigation support both have positive effect on short-term changes in public sector frauds in Nigeria. This means that increasing litigation support and Data mining raises public sector frauds in Nigeria in the short run.

Table 4.6: Results for Forensic Accounting and Private Sector Frauds in Nigeria

Variable	Investigative Accounting			Data Mining			Litigation Support		
	Coeff.	t-Stat.	Prob.	Coeff.	t-Stat.	Prob.	Coeff.	t-Stat.	Prob.
<i>Short run</i>									
ΔIVAD				3.154	3.00	0.01			
ΔIVAD _{t-1}				-2.098	-1.78	0.08			
ΔLITD							7.910	4.38	0.00

$\Delta LITD_{t-1}$							4.119	2.25	0.03
$\Delta LIVAP$							2.809	4.08	0.00
$\Delta LIVAP_{t-1}$							-0.805	-1.80	0.08
$\Delta LIVAP_{t-2}$							-0.769	-1.87	0.07
$\Delta LITP$	-0.170	-2.76	0.01	-0.172	-3.23	0.00	-0.046	-0.78	0.44
$\Delta LITP_{t-1}$				0.308	3.60	0.00	-13.413	-4.95	0.00
$\Delta LITP_{t-2}$				0.151	2.55	0.02			
ECM_{t-1}	-0.312	-6.08	0.00	-0.509	-6.86	0.00	-0.180	-4.91	0.00
<i>Long run</i>									
IVAD	-26.58	-3.06	0.00						
DATD				-20.96	-5.65	0.00			
LITD							2.30	0.15	0.88
LIVAP	-15.17	-2.77	0.01	-4.264	-1.76	0.09	20.95	0.77	0.45
LITP	-1.136	-2.61	0.01	-1.505	-4.54	0.00	-0.806	-1.14	0.27
DATP	-0.231	-0.83	0.41	-0.453	-2.19	0.04	0.766	1.12	0.27
C	13.29	0.95	0.35	39.81	3.21	0.00	24.78	0.58	0.56
Adj. R-sq.	0.453			0.582			0.432		
D.W-stat.	1.627			2.027			1.961		

The long run results in Table 4.7 shows that the coefficients of IVAD and DATD are both significant at the 1 percent level. This shows that both Investigative accounting and data mining exert significant negative effect on private sector frauds in the long run. Essentially a sustained increase in data mining is shown to significantly reduce private sector frauds in Nigeria after all adjustments have been made in the long run. Thus, data mining, although raises private sector frauds in the short run, but is tends to address the problem of private sector frauds over time in Nigeria. The coefficient of Litigation support failed the significance test at the 5 percent level. This shows that long run changes in private sector frauds do not respond to changes in Litigation support in Nigeria. This by implication imply litigation against fraudulent persons by regulatory agencies in Nigeria do not deter fraudsters. The coefficients of effectiveness of investigative accounting and effectiveness of Litigation support are both significant and negative, indicating that increase use of both investigative accounting and Litigation support will lead to reduction in Private sector frauds in Nigeria in the long run thereby showing effectiveness of these tools

4.5 Post Estimation Tests

4.5.1 Multicollinearity Tests

Given that the explanatory variables in the models are all macroeconomic in nature, there is the need to test the probability of multicollinearity in the estimates. It should be noted that multicollinearity tends to amplify the standard errors of the estimates and render the reliability of the estimated models quite low. In Table 4.12, the results of the multicollinearity test for the each of the models results (containing the six variables separately) are presented. In the result, only the centred variance inflation factors (CVIF) variables are reported since each of the equations contains a constant term. The VIF value must be less than 5.0 for the variable in an equation to be free from collinearity. In the report on Table 4.12, the Centred VIF values for all the variables are less than 5.0. Thus, it can be seen that the estimated coefficients for the equations do not integrate excessively among themselves and the estimates are therefore reliable.

Table 4.12: Post Estimation Test Results

Variable	IVAD	DATD	LITD
IVAD	2.233		
DATD		3.044	

LITD			1.560
IVAP	3.253	3.791	2.933
LITP	2.662	3.102	2.400
DATP	3.457	4.029	3.117

4.5.2 Tests for Stability of Regression

The stability of the estimated coefficients is critical for the ramification of the long run relationships. If the estimates are not stable, the effects of each of the variables are likely to deviate from the estimated relationships after a while. Hence, there is the need to examine the stability and long run steady states of the estimated coefficients in the models. The initial form of tests for stability is conducted by observing the residuals from the estimates in terms of their serial correlation and normality. The normality test is also conducted using the J-B procedure since this test also helps to determine stability of estimates. Note that the serial correlation tests are performed using the LM statistics. The results for all the estimates are presented in Table 4.13. From the results, none of the J-B and LM statistics passed the significance test even at the 5 percent level which implies that the null hypothesis is accepted in both cases. The null hypothesis is the absence of non-normality and serial correlation respectively. Thus, the tests indicate that the residuals are normally distributed and are devoid of serial correlation. Thus, each of the estimated equations can be adjudged to be stable and effective for long term prediction and analysis.

Table 4.13: Post estimation test results for serial correlation and normality

<i>Model</i>	<i>Test</i>	<i>Stat. (prob)</i>
<i>PRSF</i>	<i>Normality test (J-B)</i>	0.73 (0.47)
	<i>Serial Correlation LM Test</i>	1.2 (0.24)

Note: p-values in parentheses.

A visual test of the stability of the estimates is also conducted using the CUSUM of squares tests. This helps to eliminate doubt about possible outlier regression for any of the groups in the sample. The charts in Figures 4.9 to 4.14 show the result of the CUSUM of squares test for recursiveness of error accumulation for private frauds. It can be seen that the CUSUM of squares line lies entirely within the dotted 5 percent significance bound line throughout the chart. This reveals that the estimations are all stable within the analysis and there are no issues of structural breaks or outlier effects in the estimations.

Fig. 4.9: CUSUM for PRSF

4.5.3 Tests of Hypotheses

The tests of the hypotheses of the study are performed within the 5 percent level of significance. The focus is on the long run estimates for each hypothesis since the long run estimates provide more stable impact measurements.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of Data Mining in Detection and Prevention of Public Sector Frauds in Nigeria

For the test of hypothesis two, the focus is on data mining and public sector frauds.

Detection of fraud using Data mining frauds is examined in this paragraph. From the result, on Table 4.6, the coefficient of DATD is negative -0.013 ($p = 0.39 > 0.05$). From the result, p-value is greater than 0.05 indicating it fails the significance test at the 5 percent level. This shows that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected in this case. Thus, the result reveal that there is no significant effect of Data mining on detection of public sector frauds in Nigeria. There is a weak insignificant relationship of Data mining by regulatory activities in detecting public sector frauds in Nigeria.

This paragraph focuses on data mining (DATP) as a forensic accounting tool in preventing public sector frauds in Nigeria. From table 4.6, there is a positive co-efficient of 0.001 and p-values $0.31 > 0.05$. From the outcome, the result is insignificant showing insignificant relationship between data mining tools used by regulatory authorities and prevention of public sector frauds in Nigeria. Based on outcome, we accept the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between data mining and prevention of public sector frauds in Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant effect of Investigative Accounting on detection and prevention of Private sector frauds in Nigeria

The test of hypothesis four is based on the estimates for Investigative Accounting and private sector frauds in the long run results in Table 4.7. In the result, the coefficient of Investigative Accounting is negative -26.58 ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$). With this result, there is a significant negative relationship between Investigative accounting and private sector frauds. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship of Investigative accounting and private sector fraud is rejected. An increase in Investigative accounting detects frauds significantly in the long run. In terms of prevention the result from table 4.7 reveals a negative co-efficient of -15.17 and p-values $0.01 < 0.05$. From the outcome, there is a significant relationship of Investigative accounting and prevention of private sector frauds in Nigeria. Thus, the hypothesis that investigative accounting does not prevent private sector fraud is rejected. An increase in investigative accounting activities reduces private sector frauds significantly.

H03: There is no significant effect of Litigation Support on Detection and Prevention of Private sector frauds in Nigeria

The hypothesis focuses on the determination of significance of Litigation support in detection and prevention of private sector frauds. From table 4.6, the coefficient is negative -2.30 ($p = 0.88 > 0.05$) for detection of private sector frauds using litigation support as a forensic accounting tool. In the results, the coefficients failed the significance test. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted for Litigation support. This implies litigation support has no significant effect on detection of private sector frauds in Nigeria. The subsection of this hypothesis focuses on the prevention of private sector frauds using Litigation support. From the result on table 4.6, the coefficient is negative -0.806 and p value = $0.27 > 0.05$. From the result, there is no significant effect of Litigation support in preventing private sector frauds in Nigeria. We therefore accept the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship. A weak insignificant relationship is established.

5. 1 Conclusion

Forensic accounting tools is deployed by regulatory agencies in the fight against fraud and corruption in Nigeria. The efficacy of this fight in curtailing fraud and corruption is debatable. However, in this study the impact of Forensic accounting tools in detecting and preventing private sector frauds in Nigeria is examined. These aspects emphasized forensic accounting roles in mitigating the incidence and number of frauds in Nigeria. Thus, the study considered the distributional outcomes of Forensic accounting in fraud management in Nigeria. In this regard, number of incidence and figures were obtained from regulatory agencies through questionnaires and content analysis. Forensic accounting tools were classified into Investigative accounting, Data Mining and Litigation support while questionnaires were administered to obtain relevant information

before coding and conversion to quantitative data. The dynamic flows in fraud figures implies that a dynamic structure was devised for the analysis and the ARDL estimation framework was adopted for the empirical analysis. The data used was primary for Forensic accounting and annual secondary data for frauds for the period of 1999 to 2024. From the analytical framework, both the long run and short run impacts of forensic accounting tools on private sector frauds in Nigeria were obtained, although the focus was on the more stable long run estimates. In general, the results from the study confirmed Forensic accounting tools can help to drive reduction of private sector frauds in Nigeria. In particular, the following conclusions were made

- a) An increase in Investigative accounting detects frauds significantly in the long run and reduces private sector frauds significantly.
- b) There is significant negative effect of data mining in detection of frauds in Nigeria. In essence, increase data mining activities significantly help in detection and reduction of private sector frauds in Nigeria
- c) There is a negative co-efficient of -0.453 and p-value $0.04 < 0.05$ in terms of prevention of frauds in the private sector in Nigeria. There is therefore significant effect of Data mining activities of regulatory agencies in prevention of private sector frauds in Nigeria
- d) Litigation support has no significant effect on detection of private sector frauds in Nigeria. Thus, implying that the judiciary and slow dispensation of cases by the courts does not help in the fight against frauds
- e) There is no significant effect of Litigation support in preventing private sector frauds in Nigeria.
- f) That Data mining and investigative accounting lead to reduction in Private sector Frauds in Nigeria. However, Litigation support has no significant effect on Private sector Frauds in Nigeria.

5.2 Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings from the study:

1. There is increased need for the private sector to strengthen internal controls and internal audit by exposing them to necessary forensic accounting tools and employment of forensic accounting experts.
2. The study has also shown that only the Data Mining Forensic accounting tool significantly helps to reduce private sector frauds in Nigeria. Thus, it is essential that the private sector should maintain a central data base of staff and information that can be useful in detecting and preventing frauds
3. Special courts should be established for speedy dispensation of fraud cases as this will boost the fights against frauds
4. Technological improvements that enhance forensic accounting should be embedded in the core curriculum for training of forensic experts as well as procurement of computer assisted and technology driven forensic accounting software's
5. Heightened regulatory oversight on private firms to curtail incidences of frauds especially tax evasion and financial statement manipulations

5.3 Suggestions for Further Study

This study focused on Forensic accounting as tools for detection and prevention of frauds in Nigeria using autoregressive distributive lag. Frauds in private sector frauds from figures obtained from regulatory agencies while forensic accounting tools used content analysis of tools used for investigation; Investigative accounting, Data mining and Litigations support obtained through questionnaires. Other studies can use different methodologies to study the effect of Forensic accounting on frauds in Nigeria. Also, other studies can use different Forensic accounting tools to study the effect of Forensic accounting on Frauds in Nigeria. This study did not adopt any moderating or control variable in examining forensic accounting nexus. This issue can be taken into consideration by other studies.

REFERENCES

1. Osmond, N. O., Donald, E., & Akamike, O. J. (2023). *Impact of fraud and financial crimes on the Nigerian economy*. Direct Research Journal of Social Science and Educational Studies, 11(5), 80–87.
2. **A. Agbo et al** (2023). *The role of forensic accounting techniques in preventing fraud in Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria*.
3. **Osunwole, O. O., Adewumi, A. A., Adeyemi, O. A., & Adekanye, T.** (2024). *Influence of Forensic Accounting on Litigation Support and Engagement in Nigeria*. *FUDMA Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*, 2(3), 63–72.
4. **Modugu, K. P., & Anyaduba, J. O.** (2013). *Forensic accounting and financial fraud in Nigeria: An empirical approach*. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(7), 281–288.
5. Ekechukwu, Chijioke; Ugwu, Timothy Chidubem; & Mbah, Paulinus Chigozie (2018). *Effect of Forensic Accounting on the Performance of the Nigerian Banking Sector*. *Journal on Banking, Financial Services & Insurance Research*, 8(5).
6. **Ogah, Idagu Joseph.** (2025). *An Empirical Study of Forensic Accounting and Fraud Management by Listed Banks in Nigeria*. **African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research**, 8(1), 16-32.
7. **Onyema, Chukwuemeka Collins; Ojo-Agbody, Ayodele A.; & Adebayo, M. Adeniyi** (2024). *Impact of Forensic Accounting on Fraud Management: An Examination of Some Selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria*. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 8(4), 1648-1661.
8. **Esonwune, Goodness Mmesoma & Ogiri, Itotenaan Henry.** (2024). *Impact of Forensic Accounting on Fraud Detection and Prevention in the Nigerian Deposit Money Banks*. *EKETE – International Journal of Advanced Research*, 2(2), March 2024.
9. Okoye, E. I., & Ndah, E. N. (2019). *Forensic accounting and fraud prevention in manufacturing companies in Nigeria*. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 7(1), 107–116.
10. Basse, E. B. (2018). *Effect of forensic accounting on the management of fraud in microfinance institutions in Cross River State*. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 9(4), 79–89.
11. **Muritala, T. A., Ijaiya, M. A., Afolabi, O. H., & Yinus, A. B.** (2020). *Fraud and bank performance in Nigeria: VAR Granger causality analysis*. *Financial Internet Quarterly*, 16(1), 20–26.
12. **Offiong, A. I., Udoka, C. O., & Ibor, B. I.** (2016). *Frauds in the Nigerian Banking Sector: A Factor-Analytic Investigation*. *International Journal of Empirical Finance*, 5(1), 55–68.
13. Akinyomi, O. J. (2012). *Examination of fraud in the Nigerian banking sector and its prevention*. *Asian Journal of Management Research*, 3(1), 184–192.
14. **Okenwa, Sarah C., & Chinecherem** (2024). *Effect of Forensic Accounting on Fraud Detection and Prevention in Nigeria*.
15. Subhi, M. S., Azhar, Z., & Azeez, B. S. (2020). *The effect of forensic accounting techniques and skills on detecting and combating financial corruption*. *Qalaa Zanist Scientific Journal*, 5(1), 329–352.
16. **Ahmed et al. (2023)**, *Forensic Accounting Techniques and Fraud Detection in Public Entities of Nigeria*. (IIARD Journal of Business and African Economy).
17. Akinyomi, O. J. (2012). *Examination of fraud in the Nigerian banking sector and its prevention*. *Asian Journal of Management Research*, 3(1), 184–192.
18. Ibor, B. I. (2016). *An empirical investigation of the human resources nexus to frauds in the Nigerian banking sector*. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 6(6), 231–247.
19. Jolaiya, O. F. (2024). *Effect of electronic fraud on the financial performance of banks in Nigeria*. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 24(4), 80–92.
20. Ugwu, J. I. (2021). *Forensic accounting and fraud control in Nigeria: A critical review*. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 12(10), 112–120.
21. Agbo, A., Idimoasho, M. G., & Kwanum, I. (2023). *The role of forensic accounting techniques in preventing fraud in deposit money banks in Nigeria*. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Investment*, 9(6), 15–23.
22. Osunwole, O. O., Adewumi, A. A., Adeyemi, O. A., & Adekanye, T. (2024). *Influence of forensic accounting on litigation support and engagement in Nigeria*. *FUDMA Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*, 2(3), 63–72.
23. Okoye, E. I., & Akamobi, N. L. (2009). *The role of forensic accounting in fraud investigation and litigation support*. *The Nigerian Academic Forum*, 17(1), 78–84.

24. Onamusi, G. E., Farouk, M. A., Uyagu, B. D., & Ekele, J. S. (2024). *Effect of digital forensic accounting technological tools on cyber financial fraud detection among quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. International Journal of Capacity Building in Education and Management*, 6(5), 45–57.
25. Garba, A. (2024). *Effect of forensic accounting on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 30(3), 83–99.
26. Edeh, M., Obinna, N. T., & Patrick, I. (2024). *Effect of forensic accounting on fraud prevention of microfinance banks in Abuja, Nigeria. Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance*, 9(6), 1–23.
27. Modugu, K. P., & Anyadusa, J.O. (2018). Forensic accounting and financial fraud in Nigeria: An empirical approach: *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 14(3), 14-22.
28. Jensen, M., & Meckling, W. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economic*, 3(4), 305-360
29. Vutumu, A., Oshota, S. O., & Akinteye, A. S. (2025). Forensic accounting, internal control impact on Nigerian public sector fraud prevention: A Descriptive Analysis. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 13(2), 781-808.
30. Vutumu, A., Oshota, S. O., & Akinteye, A. S. (2025). Forensic accounting, internal control impact on Nigerian public sector fraud prevention: A Descriptive Analysis. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 13(2), 781-808.
31. Okoye, K. R. E., & Mbanugo, C. I. (2020). Forensic Accounting a tool for fraud detection and prevention in the public tertiary institutions in South East Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 7(6).
32. Oladipo, O. (2023). Banks lose N6bn to fraud in six months –Report. *Business Day*, 29th August, 2023. <https://businessday.ng/companies/article/banks-lose-n6bn-to-fraud-in-six-months-report/>
33. Omolaoye, S. (2022). N109bn fraud: how suspended accountant-general compromised TSA, IPPIS, for personal gains -EFCC. *The Guardian*, 29th July, 2022. July, 2022. <https://guardian.ng/news/n109bn-fraud-how-suspended-accountant-general-compromised-tsa-ippis-for-personal-gains-efcc/>
34. Osunwole, O. O., Adeyemi, O. A. & Dunsin, A. T. (2020). Forensic Accounting and Fraud Mitigation in the Manufacturing Industry in Nigeria. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 12(2), 23 –30.
35. Oyedokun, G. E., Enyi, P. E. & Dada, S. O. (2018). Forensic accounting techniques and integrity of financial statements: An investigative approach. *Journal of African Interdisciplinary Studies (JAIS)*2(3), 23-47.
36. Ozigbo, S. A. & Orife, C. O. (2023). Forensic Accounting and Prevention of Corporate Fraud: A Survey of Selected Firms in Delta State, *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 24(2b), 251-255
37. Safiyanu, S., Safiyanu, S. I. & Armaya’u, A. S. (2019). The Effect of Forensic Accounting Investigation in Detecting Financial Fraud: A Study in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business & Social Sciences*, 9(2), 545-553.
38. Sulaiman T. H., Ajiteru, S. A. R. & Abalaka, J. N. (2023). Forensic Accounting and Fraud Detection and Prevention in Nigerian Public Sector Using Federal Capital Territory, Abuja –Nigeria as Case Study. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Development Education and Science Research*, 7(1), 172-189.
39. Ogundana, O., Okere W., Ogunleye O., & Oladapo, I. (2018). Forensic accounting and fraud prevention and detection in Nigerian banking industry. *COJ Reviews & Research*, 1(1).
40. Okafor, O. G., Obiora, F. & O, JKJ (2022). Impact of forensic audit and financial statement fraud of deposit money bank in Nigeria. *International Academy Journal of Management, Marketing and Entrepreneurial Studies*, 9(1), 88-98
41. Obiora, F. C., Onuora, J. K. J. & Amodu O. A. (2022). Forensic accounting services and its effect on fraud prevention in Health Care Firms in Nigeria. *World Journal of Finance and Investment Research*, 6(1) 16-28.
42. Henry, A. W., & Ganiyu, A. B. (2017). Effect of forensic accounting services on fraud reduction in the Nigerian banking industry. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 4(12) 53- 64.
43. Enofe, A. O., Utomwen, O. A. & Danjuma, E. J. (2021). The role of forensic accounting in mitigating financial crimes. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research - Social Sciences and Education*, 2(3) 18-35.
44. Alhassan, I. (2020), forensic accounting and fraud detection and prevention in the Nigerian public sector. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 5(4), 108-115
45. Adeniyi A. A., (2016) Forensic auditing and financial fraud in Nigerian deposit money banks (DMBS). *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 4(8), 1-19,
46. Okoye, E.I., & Gbegi, D.O. (2013). Forensic accounting: A tool for fraud detection and prevention in the public sector. (A study of selected ministries in Kogi state). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3 (3), 1-19

47. A.O. (2013). Forensic accounting and fraud prevention in Nigerian public sector. *International Journal of Accounting research*.
48. Modugu, K.P., & Anyaduba, J.O (2013). Forensic accounting and financial fraud in Nigeria: An empirical approach. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(7), 281-289.
49. Fayyad, U., Piatetsky-Shapiro, G., & Smyth, P. (2006). From data mining to knowledge discovery in databases. *AI Magazine*, 17(3), 37–54.
50. Albrecht, W. S., Albrecht, C. C., Albrecht, C. O., & Zimbelman, M. F. (2012). *Fraud examination* (4th ed.). Cengage Learning.
51. Chigozie, P.M (2018). Effect of forensic accounting on the performance of Nigerian banking sector. *Journal of Business and Financial Studies*, 8(5), 123-135.
52. Ojuye, J.A. (2019). Forensic accounting techniques for effective investigation of corrupt practices in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Forensic Accounting and Fraud prevention*.
53. Adegbite, S.A., Benjamin, R.D., and Enyi, P. (2023). Forensic accounting techniques and fraud prevention in listed insurance companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Forensic Accounting and Fraud Investigation*, 5(1), 56-82.
54. Modugu, K.P., & Anyaduba, J.O (2013). Forensic accounting and financial fraud in Nigeria: An empirical approach. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(7), 281-289.
55. Ogbaini, A. C. ., Akpor, A. A. ., Oboh, R. ., Oputa, J. E. ., & Marvis, V. B. (2024). The Role of Forensic Accounting in Fraud Detection and Prevention in Nigerian Public Sector: A Case Study of Lagos, Nigeria. *Pedagogik: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 19(1), 71–83. <https://doi.org/10.33084/pedagogik.v19i1.7005>
56. Zakari, B.Y., & Oyedokun, G.E. (2023). Enhancing public confidence in audit reports of listed companies in Nigeria through forensic audit. *Journal of Forensic Accounting and Fraud Investigation*, 5(1), 83-103.
57. Adeola, O. (2023). Impact of forensic accounting on fraud detection in deposit money banks in Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of financial fraud*, 15(2), 123-145.
58. Rahaf Alkhalailah, Hashem Alshurafat, Husam Ananzeh, Hamzeh Al Amosh, (2024). The impact of external auditors with forensic accounting competencies on auditee firm performance, *Heliyon*, 10(11), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e32099>.
59. Onamusi, O. U., Farouk, M. A., Uyagu, B. D., & Ekele, J. S. (2024). Effects of Forensic Accounting Tools on Fraud Prevention in Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research* , 10(5), 18-31. Retrieved from <https://journals.rcmss.com/index.php/ijpamr/article/view/1079>
60. Roselyn Afor, Haruna & Akwu-Odo Salihu, Aruwa Suleiman & Eni-Itan Titilayo, Fowokan & Karimu Moses, Ibrahim, 2021. "Forensic Accounting Techniques And Fraudulent Practices In Nigerian Public Sector," *Journal of Forensic Accounting & Fraud Investigation (JFAFI)*, Association of Forensic Accounting Researchers (AFAR), vol. 6(1), 1-22, January-
61. OLOWOSEUNRE D. F., & ADEWOYE J. O. (2024). EFFECT OF FORENSIC ACCOUNTING MECHANISM ON FRAUD CONTROL IN SELECTED NIGERIAN FEDERAL GOVERNMENT PARASTATALS IN SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA. *International Journal of Financial Research and Business Development*, 3(7). Retrieved from <https://mediterraneanpublications.com/mejfrbd/article/view/305>
62. GABRIEL, A (2021). Forensic Accounting And Its Influence On Fraud Detection And Prevention In Nigeria (A Study Of First Bank Plc). Repository.mouau.edu.ng: Retrieved Jun 21, 2025, from <https://repository.mouau.edu.ng/work/view/forensic-accounting-and-its-influence-on-fraud-detection-and-prevention-in-nigeria-a-study-of-first-bank-plc-7-2>
63. Olamilekan Olayinka Joseph1*, Saka Tunde Abdulsalam1, Sunday Timothy Aboyeji2, Paul Bamikole Adesina (2024). Effect of Forensic Accounting on Fraud Detection and Prevention in Nigeria Deposit Money Bank: A Case Study of First Bank Plc. *Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management* DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36347/sjebm.2024.v11i11.004>
64. OKENWA, O (2024). Effect Of Forensic Accounting On Fraud Detection And Prevention In Nigeria: - Okenwa, Sarah C. Repository.mouau.edu.ng: Retrieved Jun 21, 2025, from <https://repository.mouau.edu.ng/work/view/effect-of-forensic-accounting-on-fraud-detection-and-prevention-in-nigeria-okenwa-sarah-c-7-2>
65. Okorafor (2024). INFLUENCE OF FORENSIC ACCOUNTING SKILLS ON FRAUD INVESTIGATION IN NIGERIAN ELECTRICITY DISTRIBUTION FIRMS. (2024). *Journal of Global Accounting*, 10(1), 227 – 262. <https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/joga/article/view/3664>

66. Nduka, Afamefuna Joseph and Manasseh, Charles and Chin, Logan (2025). ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF FORENSIC AUDITING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF QUOTED BANKS IN NIGERIA (April 17, 2025). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5234012> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5234012>
67. Vutummu, A. , Oshota, S. and Akinteye, A. (2025) Forensic Accounting, Internal Control Impact on Nigerian Public Sector Fraud Prevention: A Descriptive Analysis. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 13, 781-808. doi: [10.4236/ojbm.2025.132041](https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2025.132041).
68. Garba , A. . (2024). IMPACT OF FORENSIC ACCOUNTING ON FRAUD DETECTION IN NIGERIAN DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS. *Journal of Advance Research in Business, Management and Accounting (ISSN: 2456-3544)*, 10(2), 16-30. <https://doi.org/10.61841/pm035a38>
69. Chukwuma, O. V. ., Ugwu, J. I., & Babalola, D. S. . (2022). Application of forensic accounting in predicting the financial performance growth of MTN mobile communication in Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Science and Economics*, 1(1), 67–76. <https://doi.org/10.56556/jescae.v1i1.86>
70. Ngong Derick Ngum (2025). An Assessment of the Influence of Forensic Accounting on the Performance of Microfinance Institutions in Mezam . *Journal of Finance and accounting*. 13(3), 95-108
71. Oranefo, P. C., & Ufaroh, P. C. (2024). Effect of Forensic Accounting on Financial Fraud in Nigeria. *Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance*, 9(1), 35–53. Retrieved from <https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/index.php/ajmaf/article/view/82>.